

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** James-Civetta**FIRST NAME:** Gloria**PROGRAM CODE:** DMCR**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access).

The author used the following software: MS Office Professional Plus on Windows 10.

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. When crafting a book title, what matters:

- Needs to be crystal clear, interesting, appropriately worded.
- Conveys the essence of what is under study.
- Provides a conceptual framework of reference for continuous reflection.
- All of the above.**¹

2. Which one correctly reflects the statement that the key elements that apply to the core of your research is:

- Ideas, discoveries and insight.

¹ Bloomberg Linda Dale and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 549.

- Findings, interpretations, conclusions and recommendations.**²
- Criticisms, consistency and logic.
- Feedback, research and interest.
3. **Which is not applicable for an abstract?**
- At least 500 word long.**³
- Title of your study.
- Data sources that formed your study.
- Research problem and methodology.
4. **Taking time to reflect on your findings and what these might possibly means requires some serious mind work. Why do you need to think about your Analysis? Which answer does not apply here?**
- To develop and strengthen your critical thinking.
- To reflect on all the issues surrounding the findings.
- To problem posing.
- To channel your voice.**⁴
5. **According to Turabian guidelines, which one of the following style of citations for a single author is in the form of bibliographical format.**

² Bloomberg and Volpe, 535.

³ Bloomberg and Volpe, 551.

⁴ Bloomberg and Volpe, 473.

- Malcolm Gladwell, *The Tipping Point: How Little Things Can Make a Big Difference* (Boston: Little Brown, 2000), 64-65.
- Gladwell, Malcolm. *The Tipping Point: How Little Things Can Make a Big Difference*. Boston. Little Brown, 2000.⁵**
- Gladwell, Malcolm 2000. *The Tipping Point: How Little Things Can Make a Big Difference*. Boston. Little Brown.
- (Gladwell 2000, 64-65).

6. **In a sentence construction, the key to a clearly written sentence is:**

- In those first seven or eight words.⁶**
- In the second sentence found in a paragraph.
- In the choice of two key words used.
- When the subject is long, complex and abstract.

7. **When first used in the text, an acronym must be introduced. Select the correctly used example from the following:**

- The American Bar Association (A.B.A) is a governing body for lawyers called to practice in America.
- The American Bar Association (ABA) is a governing body for lawyers called to practice in America.⁷**

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 91 and 129.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Ninth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 114–15.

⁷ EUCLID, *ACA-401D Coursepack*. Period 1 (Bangui, Central Africa Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 44.

- The ABA (The American Bar Association) is a governing body for lawyers called to practice in America.
 - The American Bar Association is a governing body for lawyers called to practice in America (ABA).
8. **One of these terms refers to the scientific method of quantitative research or ‘empirical science’.**
- Pragmatism.
 - Interpretivism.
 - Postpositivism.⁸**
 - Critical Theory.
9. **Identify the one in the right order. The context of a dissertation begins with:**
- Problem, analysis and conclusion.
 - Research question, purpose and methodology.
 - Problem, methodology and purpose.
 - Problem, purpose and research question.⁹**
10. **Select the one with correct use of comma.**
- Use a comma to bracket phrases that are not essential to a sentence’s meaning.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 120–23.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 236.

- To join two independent clauses, use a comma followed by a conjunction, a semicolon alone, or a semicolon followed by a sentence modifier.¹⁰**
- Use a comma before ‘than’ when making a comparison.
- A comma should separate a subject from its verb.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Euclid University. *ACA-401D Coursepack, Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University Press, 2019.
- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*. SAGE Publications, 2019.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Eighth Edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.
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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ EUCLID, 17.